

INTERESTING METHODS OF LEARNING NEW WORDS

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Abstract: While English continues to be the language of science, technology, international business, research, and scholarly publishing, strategies for effective English language teaching and learning will continue to be of great interest to English language teachers and students, and perhaps English language learners. Given the importance of having extensive vocabulary knowledge, knowing many English words, especially common words, many if not all English language learners from all over the world are very interested in knowing this and understanding how to learn English vocabulary effectively.

Key words and expressions: vocabulary, stickies, repetition, learning styles

It is undeniable fact that learning new vocabulary always is problematic for learners. Despite of studying grammar deeply, language learners cannot communicate without basic vocabulary, for this reason, I decided to write this article which is based on my top techniques for learning new words.

The 4 best techniques for learning vocabulary.

Stickies everywhere.

Sticky notes are made to serve as reminders. First of all you should write down new words on sticky notes and you should stick them everywhere which in your home or workplace.

2. Flashcards.

I really love flashcards. I find it one of the most judicious as well as appealing method. You should write new words on the paper and translation or definition of this word is written on the back side of the paper. I can say it is not just the method, it is actually game. You can play it with your peers or in a group. I also use this method for my students.

3. Work in a context.

The next method is grouping words. It is easier to learn words, when they have something in common. It can be the same topic like (weather, spring, cold, winter, etc.) or synonyms and antonyms of this word such as (good, well, nice, beautiful-ugly). Learning synonyms together helps to get the nuances of meaning.

There are a number of methods which can help improve our vocabulary, however it is not the matter, just imagine, you are language learner and you have enough vocabulary all of them are passive. It is worthless. Learning tons of words is not matter but making them active is crucial. These techniques that I have mentioned above are proved by myself.

In conclusion, in order to memorize words, we need to be able to use more of those word-related sentences.

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